

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	547869 (2020 round)
Principle Investigator	Adrian Sanchez Fernandez
Structure/Description	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>98% D</p> <p>90% D (monohydrate)</p> </div>
Code	AEL03065
Producer	Anna Leung
Mass	400 mg
% Deuteration	98% on the methyl groups; 90% on the aromatic ring)
Analyses	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of choline- d_9 salicylate- d_4 (AEL03065) in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ (400 MHz).

Figure 2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of choline- d_9 salicylate- d_4 (AEL03065) in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ (400 MHz).

Apex Mass Spectrum of Peak 0.296 of AEL03045.D

Figure 3. ESI-MS(-) of salicylic acid- d_4 (AEL03045): m/z calculated for $C_7H_2D_4O_3 [M-H]^-$ as 141.1; found: 141.1 (most abundant isotopologue).

Calculation of % Deuteration from MS Isotope Distribution									
Note: Always label the lowest m/z peak as Peak No. 1 & increment each subsequent peak by 1 m/z unit									
Parent Ion Peak No.	Theoretical % D for Peak	Peak Area	Corrected Peak Area	Contribution of Peak to Overall % D	¹³ C Isotopic Distribution from ChemDraw:		Theoretical % D for Peak	Corrected Peak Area	Amount (%) of compound at Theoretical % D
1	25,0	6,0000E-01	6,0000E-01	0,1	¹³ C # 2	6,6	25,0	6,0000E-01	0,4
2	50,0	7,2000E+00	7,1604E+00	2,4	¹³ C # 3	0	50,0	7,1604E+00	4,9
3	75,0	4,3200E+01	4,2725E+01	21,7			75,0	4,2725E+01	28,9
4	100,0	1,0000E+02	9,7149E+01	65,8			100,0	9,7149E+01	65,8
5			0,0000E+00	0,0	Total Corrected Area of all Isotopic Peaks		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
6			0,0000E+00	0,0	1,4763E+02		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
7			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
8			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
9			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
10			0,0000E+00	0,0	Average % Deuteration of Molecule		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
11			0,0000E+00	0,0	90,0		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
12			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
13			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
14			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
15			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
16			0,0000E+00	0,0	Error = +/- 2 %		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
17			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
18			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
19			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
20			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
21			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
22			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
23			0,0000E+00	0,0	Input Data		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
24			0,0000E+00	0,0	Calculated		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
25			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
26			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
27			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
28			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
29			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
30			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0

Figure 4. Calculation of deuteration percentage of salicylic acid-*d*₄ (AEL03045) based on ESI-MS.